

FAUST AND REACTIVE FUNCTIONS: A TRACED PROP OF SIGNALS AND SIGNAL RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

I propose a categorical interpretation of the algebra presented by Orlarey et al in their paper An Algebra For Block Diagrams [1]. The category in question is the Traced Prop of Relations on Signals. Where Sequential and Parallel composition are relational composition and monoidal product respectively, and Recursive composition is a combination of these, the Trace and more. In this interpretation reactive functions correspond to signal processors. I prove the theorem that the trace of any delayed reactive function is a reactive function. This makes explicit the need for an implicit delay in the definition of Recursion. Furthermore, I show, by way of preserving reactivity and functionality, that each of the five main FAUST operators returns a valid signal processor when fed two of them.

1. INTRODUCTION

FAUST is a functional programming language designed for digital signal processing and ensuring the longevity of digital music tools. Often functional languages are built on solid mathematical foundations. FAUST is no exception. Orlarey et al provide a denotational semantics in their paper An Algebra For Block Diagrams [1]. In this paper I aim to give an account of FAUST by providing a correspondence between it and traced monoidal categories. I will use this to show explicitly why the recursion operator is well-defined and a formal justification for the use of a 1-sample delay. Furthermore, I will use the correspondence to provide atomic decompositions of the five FAUST operators Sequential, Parallel, Merge, Split and Recursion.

Recently there has been considerable interest in algebraic and graphical accounts of systems, like the work of Orlarey et al. Especially in the literature focused on String Diagrams: Joyal et al introduced traced monoidal categories [2], Bonchi et al applied this to create the resource calculus, a string diagrammatic language, for use in concurrency theory [3], and in Picturing Quantum Processes Coecke et al use string diagrams to teach quantum theory [4].

I will use a categorical interpretation to find interesting and rigorous mathematical answers to questions you might not have thought to ask. Such as, whether the five basic composition operators in FAUST will always return a valid signal processor when given two such processors. Questions like these should be investigated exactly because they have seemingly obvious answers. They test the foundations of FAUST and their answers provide a deeper understanding which might lead to innovation and discovery in the future.

To answer questions such as these, one needs a model for signals, signal processors and processor composition operators. The model I put forward is the Traced Prop of Relations on Signals (Sections

3 and 4). Where objects are tuples of signals and morphisms are relations on signal tuples. This puts the emphasis on how computation happens instead of what is being computed. Furthermore, composition and monoidal product are the analogues of the Sequential and Parallel operators respectively. The Merge and Split operators can be built from these with a few primitive processors. The Recursion operator can be constructed with the trace, composition, monoidal product and some more primitives. The mathematical analogue for signal processors will be reactive functions, a subset of the signal relations. In the literature these also go by the name causal functions ([5]).

We begin with a prop \mathcal{S} of relations on tuples of signals. This provides structure to support the Sequential, Parallel, Merge, Split and Recursion operators. FAUST programs are deterministic, so relations are not a suitable vehicle to model them. Instead, we will employ reactive functions, which always give a certain output for a fixed input, depend on past input and do not predict future input. These are indeed morphisms in our prop. We will show that they are closed under all operators except for feedback; decomposing the operators into more atomic elements allows us to show this. Feedback, in the sense of a trace on a monoidal category, unfortunately has the potential to return something that is not a function. But, we can recover closedness by the familiar inclusion of a 1-sample delay; this is the remit of Theorem 1.

The main contributions of this paper are the proof of Theorem 1: The trace of any delayed reactive function is a reactive function, that all five of FAUST's operators are closed with respect to reactive functions and the algebraic decompositions of these operators.

To begin with I will provide some preliminary information in Section 2. Such as, explanations for the notation you will see and necessary definitions for signals, processors and the five main composition operators in FAUST. I have used definitions from An Algebra for Block Diagrams, and from the FAUST documentation website for the signals and composition operators. And I have tried to use the same notation where it is possible and does not lead to confusion. [1], [6] Lastly, Section 7 provides some concluding remarks.

2. PRELIMINARIES

The first step in developing a mathematical model is to gain a detailed understanding of what is being modelled. This section therefore is devoted to a basic understanding of FAUST via preliminary definitions for signals, signal processors and its five composition operators. Much of the information gathered here is derived from the Faust Documentation and An Algebra for Block Diagrams by Orlarey et al. [6], [1]

2.1. Signals and Signal Processors

Unless otherwise stated, in this paper $\mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$.

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Signals are discrete functions of time. \mathbb{S} is the set of all signals, a signal tuple of size m is an element of the cartesian product \mathbb{S}^m .

$$\mathbb{S} := \{s : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}.$$

Equivalently, one could use \mathbb{Z} as the domain and state that $s(t) = 0 \forall t < 0$. This would allow a non-recursive definition of delay, but would entail dealing with an 'infinite history' of zeros. One could also use sequence notation $s = (s_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. However, I will stick with the uncomplicated version provided by Orlarey et al. In a diagram the indexing of inputs and outputs will start at 1 on the lowest signal count up to the highest one.

Signal Processors are functions on signal tuples. \mathbb{P} denotes the set of all signal processors.

$$\mathbb{P} := \bigcup_{n, m \geq 0} \{p : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^n\}.$$

$\mathbf{IO}ins(p)$ and $outs(p)$ return the number of inputs or outputs of a given signal processor, below is a formal definition.

$$\begin{aligned} ins() : \mathbb{P} &\rightarrow \mathbb{N} : ins(p : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^n) = m \\ outs() : \mathbb{P} &\rightarrow \mathbb{N} : outs(p : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^n) = n \end{aligned}$$

2.2. Faust Operators

Sequential Composition: (fig. 1) for compatible processors B and C , $B : C$ will link the outputs of B with the inputs of C . B 's first output will supply C 's first input, etc. B and C are compatible if $outs(B) = ins(C)$.

Merge Composition: (fig. 2) for compatible processors B and C , $B : > C$ will sum collections of B 's outputs and pass the results to C 's inputs. B and C are compatible if $outs(B) = k \times ins(C)$. Outputs b and β of B are in the same collection if $b \equiv \beta \pmod{ins(C)}$. The sum of a collection with representative b is passed to input c of C if $c \equiv b \pmod{ins(C)}$.

Split Composition: (fig. 3) for compatible processors B and C , $B < : C$ will copy a given output of B to possibly many inputs of C . B and C are compatible if $k \times outs(B) = ins(C)$. An output b of B supplies an input c of C if $c \pmod{outs(B)} \equiv b$.

Parallel Composition: (fig. 4) for any two processors, B, C stacks C on top of B . The resulting processor A will have $ins(A) = ins(C) + ins(B)$, where an input i of A corresponds to input i of C if $i \leq ins(C)$ or to input $j = i - ins(C)$ of B otherwise. The same goes for A 's outputs.

Recursive Composition: (fig. 5) for compatible processors B and C , $B \sim C$ creates processor A based on a feedback relationship. The first $ins(C)$ outputs of B are duplicated. One copy supplies the inputs of C , whose outputs first pass through a one-sample delay before supplying the first $outs(C)$ inputs of B . The other copy is merged with B 's unduplicated outputs to become the outputs of A . B and C are compatible if $ins(B) \geq outs(C)$ and $outs(B) \geq ins(C)$. The inputs of A are the last $ins(B) - outs(C)$ inputs of B .

As you can see, each composition operator has their own compatibility rules. In particular, any two processors may be composed in parallel, but you may only compose two processors in sequence if the output of one matches the input of another. These are exactly

Figure 1: Sequential Composition. [1]

Figure 2: Merge Composition. [1]

the requirements for combining morphisms by monoidal product and by composition in monoidal categories. This is explored further in Section 3.

Furthermore, there is an obvious hierarchy of complexity. We have Parallel and then Sequential with the two least complex descriptions. Next we have Split and Merge, which seem to be two different ways of generalising Sequential composition. Consider their notations $< : >$ and what happens when we set $k = 1$. This suggests that Split and Merge are not atomic and could be decomposed into less complex entities. This is explored further in Section 3.4. Lastly, Recursion is the most complex by far. In fact, recursion seems to behave like a trace in a traced category. This is explored in Section 6.

2.3. Useful Functions

I have collected the following functions here because they are used throughout the paper.

Gluing is the parallel composition of signal tuples. In a diagram it aligns the signals vertically putting the first argument below the second. For $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{S}^m$, $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{S}^n$, we define this index-wise

$$\begin{aligned} || : (\mathbb{S}^m \times \mathbb{S}^n) &\rightarrow \mathbb{S}^{m+n} \\ (\mathbf{x} || \mathbf{y})_i &= \begin{cases} \mathbf{y}_{i-m}, & \text{for } i > m \\ \mathbf{x}_i, & \text{for } i \leq m. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

I chose to use $||$ for parallel alignment instead of a comma as in FAUST to distinguish many signals in parallel from consecutive elements within a signal $s = (s(0), s(1), \dots)$.

Restrict takes a signal tuple and a time-step as input and cuts off all the values of the tuple after the time-step. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x}(0), \mathbf{x}(1), \dots) \in \mathbb{S}^m$

$$\begin{aligned} \upharpoonright n : \mathbb{S}^m &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}, \\ \mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n &= (\mathbf{x}(0), \dots, \mathbf{x}(n)). \end{aligned}$$

That is $\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n$ gives the first $n + 1$ m -tuples of values of the signal \mathbf{x} . For example, let the signal $x = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ then $x \upharpoonright 1 = 0, 1$.

Restrict obviously distributes over Gluing. That is, for $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{S}^m$ we have

$$(\mathbf{x} || \mathbf{y}) \upharpoonright n = (\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n) || (\mathbf{y} \upharpoonright n).$$

Figure 3: Split Composition. [1]

Figure 4: Parallel Composition. [1]

Restrict also lets us define partial evaluation for a signal processor. Let $k, m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ then the partial evaluation of a signal $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{S}^m$ at time n by a processor $p : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^k$ is

$$p(\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n) := p(\mathbf{x}) \upharpoonright n.$$

Slicing takes a signal tuple, and start and end indices as input. It cuts off the signals in the tuple that are above or below the provided indices. Let $a, b, m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $a \leq b \leq m$ and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{S}^m$, then

$$\begin{aligned} [a : b] : \mathbb{S}^m &\rightarrow \mathbb{S}^{b-a+1} \\ \mathbf{x}[a : b] &= \mathbf{x}_a || \dots || \mathbf{x}_b. \end{aligned}$$

Slicing and Restriction too may be composed in either order. That is for $a, b, m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{S}^m$ we have

$$(\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n)[a : b] = (\mathbf{x}[a : b]) \upharpoonright n.$$

Delay is defined inductively as follows. For all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\Delta_{\mathbb{S}^m}(\mathbf{x}) \upharpoonright n = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } n = 0 \\ 0, (\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n - 1), & \text{for } n > 0. \end{cases}$$

In other words, the delay shifts the time-step of all the values of \mathbf{x} up by one and then inserts a 0 at beginning. For example, let $x \in \mathbb{S}$ be the constant stream of 1s, then $\Delta_{\mathbb{S}}(x) = 011111\dots$

2.4. Reactivity

Faust programs process audio signals in real-time, and so the model should reflect this. A signal processor cannot predict the future, thus its output may only be based on what it has already seen. As a consequence, if a signal processor is given two inputs that start the same but are ultimately different, the two outputs should be identical at least until the time when the inputs first differ in value. This notion is formalised below:

A processor $p : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^k$ is **reactive** if, for $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{S}^m$ satisfying $\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n = \mathbf{y} \upharpoonright n$, for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \upharpoonright n = p(\mathbf{y}) \upharpoonright n.$$

Here I present a quick example of how to prove that signal processors are reactive.

Figure 5: Recursive Composition. [1]

Lemma 1. $\Delta_{\mathbb{S}^m} : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^m$ and $id_{\mathbb{S}^m} : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^m$ are reactive functions for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. Suppose $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{S}^m$ and $\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n = \mathbf{y} \upharpoonright n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

$$id_{\mathbb{S}^m}(\mathbf{x}) \upharpoonright n = \mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n = \mathbf{y} \upharpoonright n = id_{\mathbb{S}^m}(\mathbf{y}) \upharpoonright n.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{\mathbb{S}^m}(\mathbf{x}) \upharpoonright n &= 0, \mathbf{x} \upharpoonright (n-1) = 0, (\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright n) \upharpoonright (n-1) \\ &= 0, (\mathbf{y} \upharpoonright n) \upharpoonright (n-1) = 0, \mathbf{y} \upharpoonright (n-1) \\ &= \Delta_{\mathbb{S}^m}(\mathbf{y}) \upharpoonright n. \end{aligned}$$

As m and n were arbitrary, the lemma is proven. \square

3. THE PROP OF RELATIONS ON SIGNALS

A Prop is a strict symmetric monoidal category, where we can define a bijection between its objects and the natural numbers and the action of the monoidal product on objects is like addition for natural numbers.

3.1. Definition of $Rel_{\mathbb{S}}$

Let $Rel_{\mathbb{S}}$ the Prop of relations on signal tuples be defined as follows. I begin with the structure of the underlying category, this includes mathematical analogues for the signal processors, their inputs and outputs and composing them in sequence. I have defined this Prop in terms of relations and not just reactive functions. This is fine because reactive functions are relations, so what holds for relations holds for reactive functions too.

- **Objects** are the natural numbers, each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ corresponds to its own set \mathbb{S}^k of all possible tuples of signals of size k .
- **Morphisms** $R : \mathbb{S}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^l$ are relations in the set $Rel_{\mathbb{S}}(\mathbb{S}^k, \mathbb{S}^l) = \{R \subseteq \mathbb{S}^k \times \mathbb{S}^l\}$.
- **Identity Morphisms** $id_k : \mathbb{S}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^k$ are just identity relations.
- **Composition of Morphisms** in $Rel_{\mathbb{S}}$ is just composition of relations, for $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{S}^k$ and $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{S}^m$, $f : \mathbb{S}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^l$ and $g : \mathbb{S}^l \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^n$ we have $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in g \circ f$ iff $g(f(\mathbf{x})) = \mathbf{y}$.

Now I add the structure necessary for a monoidal category. This provides a mathematical analogue for composing in parallel.

- **Monoidal Product on Objects** is defined by addition, $\mathbb{S}^k \otimes \mathbb{S}^l = \mathbb{S}^{k+l}$.
- The **Identity Object** is the singleton set containing the empty tuple \mathbb{S}^0 .
- **Monoidal Product on Morphisms** stacks them in parallel, for $(\mathbf{x}, f(\mathbf{x})) \in f : \mathbb{S}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^l$ and $(\mathbf{y}, g(\mathbf{y})) \in g : \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^n$ we have $(\mathbf{x} || \mathbf{y}, f(\mathbf{x}) || g(\mathbf{y})) \in f \otimes g : \mathbb{S}^{k+m} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^{l+n}$.

- The **Associator** for \mathbb{S}^k , \mathbb{S}^l and \mathbb{S}^m is the identity on \mathbb{S}^{k+l+m} , $a_{k+l+m} : \mathbb{S}^{k+l} \otimes \mathbb{S}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^k \otimes \mathbb{S}^{l+m} = id_{k+l+m}$
- The **Left and Right Unitors** are identities, $l_k : \mathbb{S}^{0+k} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^k = id_k = r_k : \mathbb{S}^{k+0} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^k$.

This last structural component adds the ability to swap and change the order of the input or output signals.

- The **Symmetry** for \mathbb{S}^k and \mathbb{S}^l are defined as $c_{k,l} : \mathbb{S}^{k+l} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^{l+k}$ where $c_{k,l}(x||y) = y||x$.

I will from now on refer to \mathbb{S}^k as k and \mathbb{S}^{k+l} as $k+l$.

3.2. Verifying Axioms of Symmetric Strict Monoidal Categories

The axioms for a category are satisfied. Namely that composition is associative. The definition we have chosen for Rel_S means it is a subcategory of \mathbf{REL} the category of sets and relations and thus a category in its own right.

3.2.1. Monoidal Structure

According to Hasegawa in [7] the monoidal product of a monoidal category must be a bifunctor $\otimes : Rel_S \times Rel_S \rightarrow Rel_S$. That is \otimes must preserve identity morphisms and composition of morphisms:

$$id_k \otimes id_l = id_{k+l} \quad (1)$$

$$(f_2 \circ f_1) \otimes (g_2 \circ g_1) = (f_2 \otimes g_2) \circ (f_1 \otimes g_1). \quad (2)$$

I claim the monoidal product satisfies both the equations. To verify the first equation consider $\mathbf{x}_i \in k$ and $\mathbf{y}_i \in l$ for $i = 1, 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{x}_2||\mathbf{y}_2) \in id_k \otimes id_l &\implies (\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \in id_k, (\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2) \in id_l \\ &\implies \mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{y}_1 = \mathbf{y}_2. \end{aligned}$$

The first implication comes from the definition of \otimes , the second from the definition of identities. By the chain of implications above we can conclude that $id_k \otimes id_l \subseteq id_{k+l}$. For the opposite inclusion consider $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) \in id_{k+l}$. Notice that there exists $\mathbf{x}_1 \in k$ and $\mathbf{x}_2 \in l$ such that $\mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{x}_2 = \mathbf{x}$, this leads to the following implication

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_1) \in id_k, (\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_2) \in id_l &\implies \\ (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) = (\mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{x}_2) &\in id_k \otimes id_l. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $id_{k+l} \subseteq id_k \otimes id_l$. And so we get the equality required.

To prove that the second equation holds consider the following logic. Let $f_1 : k_1 \rightarrow l_1$, $f_2 : l_1 \rightarrow m_1$, $g_1 : k_2 \rightarrow l_2$ and $g_2 : l_2 \rightarrow m_2$. Let $\mathbf{x}_1 \in k_1$, $\mathbf{x}_2 \in m_1$, $\mathbf{y}_1 \in k_2$ and $\mathbf{y}_2 \in m_2$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{x}_2||\mathbf{y}_2) \in (f_2 \circ f_1) \otimes (g_2 \circ g_1) &\iff \\ (\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \in f_2 \circ f_1, (\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2) \in g_2 \circ g_1 &\iff \\ (\mathbf{x}_1, f_1(\mathbf{x}_1)) \in f_1, (f_1(\mathbf{x}_1), \mathbf{x}_2) \in f_2, & \\ (\mathbf{y}_1, g_1(\mathbf{y}_1)) \in g_1, (g_1(\mathbf{y}_1), \mathbf{y}_2) \in g_2 &\iff \\ (\mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{y}_1, f_1(\mathbf{x}_1)||g_1(\mathbf{y}_1)) \in f_1 \otimes g_1, & \\ (f_1(\mathbf{x}_1)||g_1(\mathbf{y}_1), \mathbf{x}_2||\mathbf{y}_2) \in f_2 \otimes g_2 &\iff \\ (\mathbf{x}_1||\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{x}_2||\mathbf{y}_2) \in (f_2 \otimes g_2) \circ (f_1 \otimes g_1) & \end{aligned}$$

The first and third ' \iff ' occur due to the definition of \otimes , while the second and fourth are due the definition of composition. The

chain of 'if and only if' statements above reveal that the second equation in (2) does indeed hold true.

Next in [7] Hasegawa states that the associator, and left and right unitors must be natural isomorphisms. This is trivially true, because for every triplet of objects (resp. single object) the associator (resp. left and right unitors) is an identity morphism. Furthermore, the associator must satisfy the pentagon commuting diagram (fig 6) and all three must satisfy the triangle commuting diagram (fig 7). However, because they are all identities they do satisfy the commuting diagrams.

Furthermore, we can conclude that this monoidal structure is strict, because the Associator and the Unitors are identity natural transformations.

Figure 6: Pentagon Diagram.

Figure 7: Triangle Diagram.

3.2.2. Symmetry Structure

The symmetry must satisfy four conditions. The first is that $c_{k,l}$ must be a bijection with inverse $c_{l,k}$. Consider that both of these symmetries are functions and that for $\mathbf{x} \in k$ and $\mathbf{y} \in l$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} c_{l,k}(c_{k,l}(\mathbf{x}||\mathbf{y})) &= c_{l,k}(\mathbf{y}||\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}||\mathbf{y} \\ c_{k,l}(c_{l,k}(\mathbf{y}||\mathbf{x})) &= c_{k,l}(\mathbf{x}||\mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}||\mathbf{x}. \end{aligned}$$

That is, $c_{l,k} \circ c_{k,l} = id_{k+l}$ and $c_{k,l} \circ c_{l,k} = id_{l+k}$. As the two symmetries are inverses of one another, we can conclude that they are bijections. And so the first condition is satisfied.

The second condition is to be a natural isomorphism with respect to the functors $= \otimes -$ and $- \otimes =$. This condition holds if the symmetry satisfies the following two equations for any $f : k \rightarrow l$ and $g : m \rightarrow n$

$$\begin{aligned} (g \otimes f) \circ c_{k,m} &= c_{l,n} \circ (f \otimes g) \\ c_{n,l} \circ (g \otimes f) &= (f \otimes g) \circ c_{m,k}. \end{aligned}$$

3.4.3. Split Composition

Recalling the definition of the '<:' Split composition from section 1, let $k, M, N, L \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathbf{x} \in M$, $p : M \rightarrow N$ and $q : kN \rightarrow L$, then

$$\begin{aligned} p < : q & : M \rightarrow L, \text{ via} \\ p < : q & : \mathbf{x} \mapsto q((p_1(\mathbf{x})) \parallel \dots \parallel (p_k(\mathbf{x}))) \\ p < : q & = q \circ (p_1 \otimes \dots \otimes p_k) \circ \gamma_{k,M}. \end{aligned}$$

In the second and third lines, I use the same enumeration for illustration technique as in (3.4.2).

3.4.4. Merge Composition

Recalling the definition of '>:' Merge composition from section 1, let $k, M, N, L \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathbf{x} \in M$, $p : M \rightarrow kN$ and $q : N \rightarrow L$, then

$$\begin{aligned} p > : q & : M \rightarrow L, \text{ defined by} \\ p > : q & : \mathbf{x} \mapsto q \left(\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \pi_{1+jN}(p(\mathbf{x})) \parallel \dots \parallel \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \pi_{N+jN}(p(\mathbf{x})) \right) \\ p > : q & = q \circ \left(\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \pi_{1+jN} \circ p \otimes \dots \otimes \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \pi_{N+jN} \circ p \right) \circ \gamma_{N,M} \end{aligned}$$

. Note that trivially addition is a reactive function.

The algebraic versions of Split and Merge operators comprise only the sequential composition and monoidal product of reactive functions. We know these preserve reactivity and functionality. So, we can conclude that the Merge and Split operators also preserve reactivity and functionality. As we can see, these two operators are not atomic but can be broken down into more atomic parts.

We can't yet describe '~' the Recursion operator. This is because Props don't have a notion of 'feedback' or 'looping'. In the next section we look at traces on Rel_S so that we can have a mathematical description of feedback.

4. TRACE ON REL_S

In this section we investigate the existence of a trace defined on the Prop of signals and relations Rel_S . We begin by defining a candidate trace via its action on signal relations. Then, we proceed to provide evidence that it satisfies all the axioms required in [7] for it to be a trace: functionality, naturality and adherence to four coherence axioms. The theory of traced monoidal categories, as seen in [7], provides an algebraic account of systems with feedback. We shall now show that Rel_S has a trace, which will let us model FAUST's recursion operator.

4.1. Definition of $Tr_{A,B}^X$

The first hypothesis in Hasegawa's definition of trace is that we are working within a balanced monoidal category. Luckily for us a Prop, a strict symmetric monoidal category, is, in particular, a balanced monoidal category.

The trace is a family of functions (we'll prove this property soon). Each function relates to a triplet of objects (A, B, X) in Rel_S as map from one set of signal relations to another.

$$Tr_{A,B}^X : Rel_S(A \otimes X, B \otimes X) \rightarrow Rel_S(A, B),$$

Figure 10: Trace Action. [7]

for $f \subseteq (A \otimes X \times B \otimes X)$

$$(a, b) \in Tr_{A,B}^X(f) \Leftrightarrow \exists x \in X \text{ s.t. } (a \parallel x, b \parallel x) \in f. \quad (3)$$

I shall refer to the above logic as the 'trace condition'.

4.2. Functionality of $Tr_{A,B}^X$

I claimed earlier that each member of this family is a function. To see that this is true, we show that each member always has an output for a given input and that this output is unique.

To see that $Tr_{A,B}^X$ always produces a relation for a given input relation, consider the set $\{(a, b) \in (A \times B) \mid \exists x \in X \text{ s.t. } (a \parallel x, b \parallel x) \in f\}$. This set is either infinite, finite or empty, in all cases it remains a subset of $(A \times B)$. Thus, the trace will always produce an output relation between A and B when given an input relation between $A \otimes X$ and $B \otimes X$.

Fix X, A , and B . Let $f \subseteq (A \otimes X) \times (B \otimes X)$. Assume, for contradiction, that $\exists g, g' \subseteq (A \times B)$ such that $g \neq g'$ and

$$Tr_{A,B}^X(f) = g \text{ and } Tr_{A,B}^X(f) = g'.$$

Without loss of generality we can assume there is a pair $(a, b) \in (A \times B)$ such that $(a, b) \in g$, but $(a, b) \notin g'$. However, by (3)

$$\begin{aligned} (a, b) \in g & \Leftrightarrow \exists x \in X \text{ s.t. } (a \parallel x, b \parallel x) \in f \\ & \Leftrightarrow (a, b) \in g', \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Thus, the assumption that g and g' are different is incorrect. This is the equivalent to saying $Tr_{A,B}^X$ has unique outputs for given inputs.

A function is a relation has existence and uniqueness of output, we have shown that $Tr_{A,B}^X$ has both these properties and we can conclude that it's a function.

4.3. Naturality

Many definitions of trace also call for the family of functions to be 'natural'. Each member must be natural in the traced and untraced variables. This property ensures that you can compose morphisms with the input being traced and then take the trace or compose with output being traced and then take the trace and still arrive at the same end product. That is, for naturality in the trace line, we want the following equation to be true.

$$Tr_{A,B}^X((id_B \otimes h) \circ f) = Tr_{A,B}^X(f \circ (id_A \otimes h)).$$

Figure 11: Naturality. [7]

This property is the same the sliding coherence condition for Joyal, Street and Verity's paper

To see that this is true, let $f \subseteq (A \otimes X) \times (B \otimes X)$, $h \subseteq X \times X$, id_A, id_B be the identity relations on A and B respectively, and suppose that $\exists a \in A, b \in B$ such that

$$(a, b) \in (Tr_{A,B}^X((id_B \otimes h) \circ f))$$

we then have that $\exists x \in X$ satisfying $(a||x, b||x) \in ((id_B \otimes h) \circ f)$, but this implies there's an $x' \in X$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (a||x, b||x') &\in f \text{ and} \\ (x', x) &\in h. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we also have that $(a||x', a||x) \in (id_A \otimes h)$, and

$$\begin{aligned} (a||x', b||x') &\in (f \circ (id_A \otimes h)) \\ \iff (a, b) &\in (Tr_{A,B}^X(f \circ (id_A \otimes h))). \end{aligned}$$

This proves naturality in the traced line.

Naturality in the untraced variables is exactly the Tightening coherence condition in 4.4.1 below. This condition ensures that composing with the untraced variables before or after taking the trace gives the same result.

4.4. Coherence Conditions

In [7], Hasegawa defines four coherence conditions that any candidate function must fulfill in order to be a trace.

4.4.1. Tightening

Satisfying this condition ensures the trace is natural with respect to the inputs and outputs not taking part in the trace. This idea is encapsulated in the following equality. Let $f \subseteq (A \otimes X) \times (B \otimes X)$, $h \subseteq A' \times A$, $k \subseteq B \times B'$, and id_X be the identity relation on X .

$$Tr_{A',B'}^X((k \otimes id_X) \circ f \circ (h \otimes id_X)) = k \circ Tr_{A,B}^X(f) \circ h \quad (4)$$

Figure 12: Tightening. [7]

Suppose that (a', b') is an element of the LHS of equation (4). By the trace condition we know $\exists x \in X$ satisfying

$$(a' || x, b' || x) \in ((k \otimes id_X) \circ f \circ (h \otimes id_X)).$$

Due to the fact that we're composing relations we know these three inclusions hold true $(a', a) \in h$, $(b, b') \in k$ and $(a || x, b || x) \in f$, for some $a \in A$ and $b \in B$. This last inclusion is exactly the condition we're looking for so $(a', b') \in (k \circ Tr_{A,B}^X(f) \circ h)$. This means we have $LHS \subseteq RHS$ from equation (4).

To get the reverse inclusion $RHS \subseteq LHS$ you can simply reverse the above logic. Furthermore, as the choices of f , h and k were arbitrary we can conclude that the tightening condition holds.

4.4.2. Yanking

The original condition is stated for balanced monoidal categories. Luckily for us, it can be simplified when working with Props because they are symmetric monoidal categories. Namely, the twists are identities, so we need not worry about them here, and for the braids we have $(c_{A,B})^{-1} = c_{B,A}$.

Therefore, we just need to show that the trace of $c_{X,X} : X \otimes X \rightarrow X \otimes X$, defined by $(\bar{x}_1 || \bar{x}_2) \mapsto (\bar{x}_2 || \bar{x}_1)$, satisfies

$$Tr_{X,X}^X(c_{X,X}) = id_X.$$

Figure 13: Yanking. [7]

To see this suppose $(x_1, x_2) \in (Tr_{X,X}^X(c_{X,X}))$ and assume for contradiction that $x_1 \neq x_2$. The definition of the trace implies $\exists x \in X$ such that

$$(x_1 || x, x_2 || x) \in c_{X,X}$$

by the definition of the symmetry we get $x_2 = x = x_1$, a contradiction. That is, $(Tr_{X,X}^X(c_{X,X})) \subseteq id_X$.

For the opposite inclusion, let $(x, x) \in id_X$. Note that $(x || x, x || x) \in c_{X,X} \iff (x, x) \in Tr_{X,X}^X(c_{X,X})$. So, $id_X \subseteq (Tr_{X,X}^X(c_{X,X}))$. Together with the above inclusion we have that $Tr_{X,X}^X(c_{X,X}) = id_X$ as required.

4.4.3. Superposing

This condition, realized in the Prop of relations is as follows, let $f \subseteq (A \otimes X) \times (B \otimes X)$ be a signal relation and id_C be the identity on C . Then, the superposing condition states

$$Tr_{C \otimes A, C \otimes B}^X(id_C \otimes f) = id_C \otimes Tr_{A,B}^X(f).$$

Figure 14: Superposing. [7]

To see that this holds, let $a \in A$, $b \in B$, $c_1, c_2 \in C$. If

$$(c_1 || a, c_2 || b) \in (Tr_{C \otimes A, C \otimes B}^X(id_C \otimes f)),$$

then $(c_1 || a || x, c_2 || b || x) \in id_C \otimes f$ for some $x \in X$. That is, $(a || x, b || x) \in f$ and $c_1 = c_2$. taking the trace of f we get

$$(c_1 || a, c_2 || b) = (c_1 || a, c_1 || b) \in id_C \otimes (Tr_{A,B}^X(f)).$$

As c , a and b were arbitrary this implies.

$$(Tr_{C \otimes A, C \otimes B}^X(id_C \otimes f)) \subseteq (id_C \otimes (Tr_{A,B}^X(f))).$$

For the opposite inclusion, suppose for some $c \in C$ that

$$(c || a, c || b) \in id_C \otimes (Tr_{A,B}^X(f)).$$

By the definition of trace, this implies that, for some $x \in X$, $(a||x, b||x) \in f$, i.e. $(c||a||x, c||b||x) \in id_C \otimes f$. By taking the trace with respect to X , we get

$$(c||a, c||b) \in (Tr_{C \otimes A, C \otimes B}^X(id_C \otimes f)).$$

Noting that $(c||a, c||b)$ was arbitrary, we get the required inclusion. Together with the previous inclusion we get that $Tr_{C \otimes A, C \otimes B}^X(id_C \otimes f) = id_C \otimes Tr_{A, B}^X(f)$ as required.

4.4.4. Exchange

This condition ensures that order in which you trace your inputs doesn't matter. I will slightly alter this conditions from that found in ([7]) by replacing $c_{Y, X}^{-1}$ with $c_{X, Y}$. Which is a valid move as the definition of symmetric monoidal categories states that the two are equal.

$$\begin{aligned} Tr_{A, B}^X(Tr_{A \otimes X, B \otimes X}^Y(f)) = \\ Tr_{A, B}^Y(Tr_{A \otimes Y, B \otimes Y}^X((id_B \otimes c_{Y, X}) \circ f \circ (id_A \otimes c_{X, Y}))) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 15: Exchange. [7]

where $c_{Y, X} : Y \otimes X \rightarrow X \otimes Y$, defined by $(y||x) \mapsto (x||y)$, $\forall (y||x) \in Y \otimes X$, is the symmetry on $Y \otimes X$, id_B and id_A are the identity relations on A and B respectively, and $f \subseteq (A \otimes X \otimes Y) \times (B \otimes X \otimes Y)$.

I claim the above equation holds true for (3). To see this, suppose $\exists a \in A, b \in B$ such that

$$(a, b) \in (Tr_{A, B}^X(Tr_{A \otimes X, B \otimes X}^Y(f)))$$

undoing the trace first with respect to X then with respect to Y gives an $x \in X$ and a $y \in Y$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (a||x, b||x) &\in (Tr_{A \otimes X, B \otimes X}^Y(f)), \text{ and} \\ (a||x||y, b||x||y) &\in (f). \end{aligned}$$

By applying the suitable symmetries to the $X \otimes Y$ inputs and outputs of f , we also have $(a||y||x, b||y||x) \in ((id_B \otimes c_{Y, X}) \circ f \circ (id_A \otimes c_{X, Y}))$. We can now take the traces with respect to X first and Y second to get

$$(a, b) \in Tr_{A, B}^Y(Tr_{A \otimes Y, B \otimes Y}^X((id_B \otimes c_{Y, X}) \circ f \circ (id_A \otimes c_{X, Y}))).$$

This proves that $LHS \in RHS$.

For the opposite inclusion, $RHS \in LHS$ simply reverse the above argument and apply the inverse symmetries

We can now rest assured that Rel_S equipped with (3) is a traceable Prop.

4.5. Trace Example

Now that we have a trace let's apply it to something. As functions are special cases of relations, there will be a trace for any function on the signal tuples. We will use the function $\delta_X : X \rightarrow X \otimes X$ defined by $\delta_X(\mathbf{x}) := \mathbf{x}||\mathbf{x}$. This function is obviously reactive. The trace of δ_X , however, is not a function.

To see this, consider $Tr_{0, X}^X(\delta_X) \subseteq 0 \times X$. Suppose $\mathbf{y} \in X$ then the pair (e, \mathbf{y}) is an element of the trace if $(e||\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}||\mathbf{x}) \in \delta_X$ for some $\mathbf{x} \in X$, obviously $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{y}$ satisfies the trace condition. But as \mathbf{y} was arbitrary this means (e, \mathbf{y}) is an element of the trace for every element $\mathbf{y} \in X$. Thus, the trace of this function is a one to many relation, and not a function.

However, all is not lost. If we compose the traced line with a one-sample delay as shown $(id_X \otimes \Delta_x) \circ \delta_X$. As with the previous example, when we take the trace $Tr_{0, X}^X((id_X \otimes \Delta_x) \circ \delta_X)$, (e, \mathbf{y}) is an element of the relation if there's an \mathbf{x} such that $(e||\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}||\mathbf{x})$. But this time we know the first value of the traced line is 0 , because of the delay. This implies the only value that can satisfy the trace condition is $0 \in X$, the zero signal. Thus, the delayed version of δ_X does in fact trace to a function. This example is part of a more general phenomenon. In the next section we will prove that delaying any reactive function is enough to ensure that trace is a reactive function.

5. TRACE OF DELAYED REACTIVE FUNCTIONS

In this section we will see that given any reactive function we need only alter its output slightly with a delay to obtain a reactive function that remains reactive and functional when we take its trace.

Definition: Delayed Reactive Function

Given a reactive function $g : X \otimes Y \rightarrow X \otimes Z$, its corresponding delayed reactive function is $f : X \otimes Y \rightarrow X \otimes Z$ defined as

$$f := (\Delta_X \otimes id_Z) \circ g \quad (5)$$

that is, f acts the same as g except that it adds a delay of one time step to the top X -tuple of g 's output streams. Furthermore, f is reactive by the results of section 3.3 and lemma 1.

I will use $tr(f) : Y \rightarrow Z$ to refer to the trace of f , instead of $Tr_{Y, Z}^X(f) : Y \rightarrow Z$. I do this to avoid cumbersome notation and because it is obvious which lines are being traced.

Theorem 1. *The trace of a delayed reactive function is a reactive function.*

The following proof is divided into three parts. Parts 1 and 2 show that the $tr(f)$ is a function by displaying the properties of existence and uniqueness respectively. Part 3 shows that it is reactive.

5.1. Proof Part 1: Existence of the Trace

Here we will prove the existence of $tr(f)(y)$ for all $y \in Y$. Remember that for $tr(f)(y)$ to exist there must be an $x^* \in X$ satisfying the trace condition:

$$f(x^*||y) = x^*||z \quad (6)$$

whence $z = tr(f)(y)$. So, the goal here is to show that for each $y \in Y$ there's an $x^* \in X$ satisfying (6).

We fix $y \in Y$ and the proceed to inductively cook up a suitable x^* as follows

$$x^* \upharpoonright n := \begin{cases} 0, & n = 0, \\ 0, g(x^* \upharpoonright (n-1) || y \upharpoonright (n-1)) [1 : X], & n > 0. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

That is we define $x^* \upharpoonright 0 := 0$ and inductively calculate $g(x^* \upharpoonright (n-1) || y \upharpoonright (n-1))$ to build $x^* \upharpoonright n$. Before we move on, we must check that the reverse direction holds true that the next inductive step does in fact contain the current one, i.e. $(x^* \upharpoonright n + 1) \upharpoonright n = x^* \upharpoonright n$. The following show this to be true

$$\begin{aligned} (x^* \upharpoonright n + 1) \upharpoonright n &= (0, g(x^* \upharpoonright n || y \upharpoonright n) [1 : X]) \upharpoonright n \\ &= 0, g(x^* \upharpoonright (n-1) || y \upharpoonright (n-1)) [1 : X] \\ &= x^* \upharpoonright n \end{aligned}$$

The first and last equalities come from (7) and the second holds true because the object being restricted to n values is $n+1$ values long and by g 's reactivity.

I claim that x^* satisfies (6). To see this, we first check the trace condition holds for $n = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x^* \upharpoonright 0 || y \upharpoonright 0) [1 : X] &= \Delta(g(x^* \upharpoonright 0 || y \upharpoonright 0) [1 : X]) \\ &= \Delta(g(x^* || y) \upharpoonright 0 [1 : X]) \\ &= 0, g(x^* || y) \upharpoonright (-1) [1 : X] \\ &= 0 \\ &= x^* \upharpoonright 0. \end{aligned}$$

In fact, the above is true for all $x \in X$, the top X tuple in the output is always 0. Next, we check the same for $n > 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x^* \upharpoonright n || y \upharpoonright n) [1 : X] &= \Delta(g(x^* \upharpoonright n || y \upharpoonright n) [1 : X]) \\ &= \Delta(g(x^* || y) \upharpoonright n [1 : X]) \\ &= 0, g(x^* || y) \upharpoonright (n-1) [1 : X] \\ &= 0, g(x^* \upharpoonright (n-1) || y \upharpoonright (n-1)) [1 : X] \\ &= x^* \upharpoonright n. \end{aligned}$$

The above two systems of equalities show that x^* satisfies the trace condition for y . Moreover, as the choice of y was arbitrary, we can conclude that for every element of Y there is an x^* satisfying the trace condition. This implies that $tr(f)(y)$ exists for all y .

5.2. Proof Part 2: Uniqueness of the Trace

In this part, we discover that the x^* defined in Part 1 is unique in its ability to satisfy (6) and conclude that $tr(f)$ is a function.

Suppose, for contradiction, that there is an $x^\dagger \in X$ such that $x^\dagger \neq x^*$ and $f(x^\dagger || y) = x^\dagger || z^\dagger$. Then, we can find a smallest index $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $x^\dagger \upharpoonright n \neq x^* \upharpoonright n$.

By minimality of n it must be true that:

$$x^\dagger \upharpoonright (n-1) = x^* \upharpoonright (n-1),$$

but that then implies the following:

$$\begin{aligned} x^\dagger \upharpoonright n &= 0, g(x^\dagger \upharpoonright (n-1) || y \upharpoonright (n-1)) [1 : X] \\ &= 0, g(x^* \upharpoonright (n-1) || y \upharpoonright (n-1)) [1 : X] \\ &= x^* \upharpoonright n. \end{aligned}$$

This is obviously a contradiction. One can recycle the above argument to disprove any candidate smallest index of inequality, and so conclude that $x^\dagger \upharpoonright n = x^* \upharpoonright n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, i.e. that $x^\dagger = x^*$, thus our assumption that x^* wasn't unique was incorrect.

It's now easy to see that setting $tr(f)(y) = z$ from 6 defines a relation that has the existence and uniqueness properties, and as such defines a function $tr(f) : Y \rightarrow Z$.

5.3. Proof Part 3: Reactivity of the Trace

In this part we show that $tr(f)$ has the reactive property as well.

Suppose, we have $x_1, x_2 \in X$, $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the following are true

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 \upharpoonright n &= x_2 \upharpoonright n \\ y_1 \upharpoonright n &= y_2 \upharpoonright n, \end{aligned}$$

then, by reactivity of f

$$\begin{aligned} tr(f)(y_1) \upharpoonright n &= f(x^* || y_1) \upharpoonright n [X + 1 : X + Z] \\ &= f(x^* || y_2) \upharpoonright n [X + 1 : X + Z] \\ &= tr(f)(y_2) \upharpoonright n. \end{aligned}$$

By combining Parts 1, 2 and 3 we can see that for a reactive function f of the form described in equation (5) taking its trace results in reactive function. That is, we can augment any reactive function we want to trace by putting a delay on the variable that we wish to trace to ensure that we get a reactive function as output. **QED**

To see that the reactivity property is needed, consider the function $\rho_M : M \rightarrow M$ defined by $\rho(\mathbf{x})(t) = \mathbf{x}(t+1) \forall t \in \mathbb{Z}$. Semantically, this function predicts the future of given signal. Importantly, ρ is not reactive, to see this suppose we have $\mathbf{x} = \dots, \mathbf{0}_{-1}, \mathbf{1}_0, \mathbf{1}_1, \mathbf{1}_2, \mathbf{1}_3, \dots$ and $\mathbf{y} = \dots, \mathbf{0}_{-1}, \mathbf{1}_0, \mathbf{1}_1, \mathbf{0}_2, \mathbf{0}_3, \dots$ in M , obviously $\mathbf{x} \upharpoonright 1 = \mathbf{y} \upharpoonright 1$. However,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\mathbf{x}) \upharpoonright 1 &= (\dots, \mathbf{1}_{-1}, \mathbf{1}_0, \mathbf{1}_1, \mathbf{1}_2, \dots) \upharpoonright 1 = \mathbf{1}_0, \mathbf{1}_1 \\ &\neq \mathbf{1}_0, \mathbf{0}_1 = (\dots, \mathbf{1}_{-1}, \mathbf{1}_0, \mathbf{0}_1, \mathbf{0}_2, \dots) \upharpoonright 1 \\ &= \rho(\mathbf{y}) \upharpoonright 1. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, $\Delta_M \circ \rho_M = id_M$, as the time-step wise definitions of the two functions cancel out (cf. section 2.4). Therefore, for δ_M as defined in Section (4.5), we have the following

$$((\Delta_M \circ \rho_M) \otimes id_M) \circ \delta_M = \delta_M$$

But, from section (4.5) we already know that the trace of this function is a not a function. This exemplifies how important reactivity is in having the trace return a reactive function.

6. UNDERSTANDING RECURSION

To summarise the last two sections, in Section 4 we augmented the Prop Rel_S with a trace to model feedback and loops, and in the last section we proved that this trace maps delayed reactive functions to reactive functions. We can now deconstruct the Recursion operator from FAUST and show that it preserves reactivity and functionality.

Recall the definition of Recursion from Section 2. One can identify four necessary signal processors from this definition. It needs two compatible processors, let these be the reactive functions $f :$

$Y + X \rightarrow Z + W$ and $g : W \rightarrow X$. It also needs a processor to duplicate the top W outputs of f , let this be the reactive function $\gamma_{2,W} : W \rightarrow W + W$. Lastly, it needs a delay to ensure that taking the trace will return a reactive function, let this be the reactive function $\Delta_X : X \rightarrow X$. With all this in mind, consider the following function $h : Y + X \rightarrow Z + W + X$, a combination of all these signal processors

$$h = (id_{Z+W} \otimes \Delta_X) \circ (id_{Z+W} \otimes g) \circ (id_Z \otimes \gamma_{2,W}) \circ f,$$

This is a reactive function because all of its components are reactive functions which have been stitched together with operators that preserve reactivity and functionality. Moreover, h is a delayed reactive function, and so $Tr_{Y,Z+W}^X(h)$ will be a reactive function too.

One can verify that h satisfies the FAUST definition of Recursion, because g feeds back into f via a one-sample delay, the W output of f is duplicated to supply g and to rejoin f 's Z output to form the overall output. This is exactly The action described by Recursive composition in Section 2. So we have

$$f \sim g = Tr_{Y,Z+W}^X((id_{Z+W} \otimes (\Delta_X \circ g)) \circ (id_Z \otimes \gamma_{2,W}) \circ f). \quad (8)$$

And we have that for any compatible reactive functions f, g , i.e. signal processors, $f \sim g$ exists, is unique and is a reactive function itself. So we can conclude that Recursive composition will always return a valid signal when given two valid signal processors. Furthermore, it is obvious now that the definition needs a delay to ensure the trace gives a reactive function.

7. CONCLUSION

We have seen that the Block Diagram Algebra can be extended to a categorical approach, namely we can model it using a traced version of Rel_S . Where this category is a Traced Prop of Relations on Signals. Using this approach we have seen that each of the five main FAUST operators will always give a valid signal processor because they preserve two key properties: functionality and reactivity.

We have also witnessed a proof of the theorem that all delayed reactive functions trace to reactive functions. This result showed that definition of the Recursion operator needs a 1-sample delay to ensure that when the trace is taken it will return a reactive function (aka a signal processor).

Furthermore, this categorical interpretation of the algebra provides evidence that the Sequential and Parallel operators are more atomic than Merge and Split, because Merge and Split can be decomposed into primitives stitched together by Sequential Parallel. The categorical interpretation also provides evidence that the Recursion operator is fundamentally different from the other four, because it requires a trace.

More research and investigations need to be conducted to ascertain whether this approach can be applied to more concrete problems such as optimisation.

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